

On Certain Theoretical Developments Underlying the Hilbert-Huang Transform^{1,2}

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Abstract—One of the main traditional tools used in scientific and engineering data spectral analysis is the Fourier Integral Transform and its high performance digital equivalent – the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). Both carry strong a-priori assumptions about the source data, such as being linear and stationary, and of satisfying the Dirichlet conditions. A recent development at the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC), known as the Hilbert-Huang Transform (HHT), proposes a novel approach to the solution for the nonlinear class of spectral analysis problems. Using a-posteriori data processing based on the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) sifting process (algorithm), followed by the normalized Hilbert Transform of the decomposed data, the HHT allows spectral analysis of nonlinear and nonstationary data. The EMD sifting process results in a non-constrained decomposition of a source numerical data vector into a finite set of Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMF). These functions form a nearly orthogonal, derived from the data basis (adaptive basis). The IMFs can be further analyzed for spectrum content by using the classical Hilbert Transform. A new engineering spectral analysis tool using HHT has been developed at NASA GSFC, the HHT Data Processing System (HHT-DPS). As the HHT-DPS has been successfully used and commercialized, new applications pose additional questions about the theoretical basis behind the HHT EMD algorithm. Why is the fastest changing component of a composite signal being sifted out first in the EMD sifting process? Why does the EMD sifting process seemingly converge and why does it converge rapidly? Does an IMF have a distinctive structure? Why are the IMFs nearly orthogonal? We address these questions and develop the initial theoretical background for the HHT. This will contribute to the development of new HHT processing options, such as real-time and 2-D processing using Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) computational resources, enhanced HHT synthesis, and will broaden the scope of HHT applications for signal processing.

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1. INTRODUCTION AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

1.1 Introduction

One of the main traditional tools used in scientific and engineering data spectral analysis is the Fast Fourier Transform. However, it carries strong a-priori assumptions about the source data, such as being both linear and stationary. The data must originate from a periodic waveform, satisfy the Dirichlet conditions of having a finite number of discontinuities and extrema, and be absolutely integrable in any sequence of time intervals with length equal to the period T [8] or the FFT may not yield physically meaningful results [15]. The EMD sifting process [1] is a novel algorithm for digital signal processing of non-linear and nonstationary data. Giving an arbitrary input vector $s = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_N)$, where s_i equals to numerical measurements $s(t_i)$ of the time-variable signal $s(t)$ at equally spaced (Δt) sampling arguments t_i (for $i=1 \dots N$), the EMD algorithm invariably sifts out IMF components of different time scales with the fastest varying component being sifted out first.

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The EMD sifting process results in a sequence of scales from the highest to the lowest scale of the processed signal, the residual. The EMD sifting process seemingly converges to an IMF before satisfying user supplied run-configuration vector (1) sifting stop parameters. The resulting IMFs form a nearly orthogonal adaptive basis and the near-orthogonality of the IMFs must be induced by some structure of the IMFs. The EMD also converges rapidly in just a few iterative passes. This has been observed in all tests conducted so far, in other words, empirically.

However, it is not obvious why the EMD algorithm behaves (works) this way. A recent paper [13] points out the difficulties in development of theoretical elements for the EMD and states the nonexistence of a theory for EMD - "... from a general perspective, there is a clear call for theoretical elements which would explain the observed [EMD] behaviors, a task which is made difficult by the fact that EMD does not admit an analytical definition, ... the purpose of this experimental study ... [is of] filling somehow the gap between a still nonexistent theory and the application of an appealing method to real-world situations".

This paper addresses these questions and provides the basic theory for HHT by examining an intuitive example of a signal containing artificially created fast and slow varying components and a few analogies. We then consider a general case for the EMD sifting process and an arbitrary signal. We establish the theoretical foundations of the EMD algorithm's sifting sequence of scales and theoretical convergence by proving the hypotheses of the fastest scale being sifted out first, of the sifting process symmetric pair invariance and resulting IMF structure, and of the sifting process theoretical rapid convergence in diminishing amplitude regions. We are also demonstrating some ideas on signal $s(t)$ synthesis, using the Intrinsic Mode Functions and the Hilbert Spectrum. We then describe a few new applications, as well as define the areas of future research work on the HHT.

1.2 Research Methodology

The HHT and its main algorithm – the EMD, are empirical algorithms. As the HHT implementation in the HHT-DPS has been successfully used and commercialized ([2], [12], [15]) new applications pose additional questions about the theoretical basis behind the HHT and, in particular, the EMD algorithm. The problem is to understand and develop the theoretical foundations of the EMD algorithm empirical behavior, which is the subject of this research paper.

We formulate the EMD algorithm in Section 2.1 by means of an in-depth procedural description of it, as it is implemented in the HHT-DPS Release 1.4. The EMD algorithm has been described in the original publications and patents [1], [3] and in [4]-[5]. However, an overview of it is given here once more, in a form closely related to its implementation in HHT-DPS, and formulated with different

procedural details for the purpose of using it to expose the theory of why the EMD empirical algorithm works. We state the research problem in Section 2.2.

We then make a few intuitive observations about the EMD algorithm behavior in Section 3 by constructing a special example for which the answer is known by other than EMD means and we propose a few hypotheses of why the EMD sifting process works. Namely, we formulate the hypothesis that EMD sifts out the fastest scale IMF components first, that the EMD sifting process preserves symmetric pairs of adjacent extremas interleaved with regions of diminishing amplitudes giving the IMFs a definitive structure (Section 4), and that the EMD algorithm converges rapidly just in a few iterative passes because of the way the median is defined in the EMD algorithm (Section 5).

We have conducted the research to find a theoretical explanation for the empirical behavior of EMD implementation in the Hilbert-Huang Transform Data Processing System and proved the related hypotheses in an earlier paper [14] and the corresponding Sections 3-5 in this paper.

This research, in turn, allowed us to develop new processing options in HHT, such as signal synthesis using IMFs and Hilbert Spectrum, based on insight into Signal-IMF-Hilbert Spectrum 1-to-1 mapping (Section 6). It further allowed us to define new areas of research for the HHT (in the Conclusions Section).

2. EMD ALGORITHM OVERVIEW AND PROBLEM STATEMENT

The EMD algorithm empirical behavior (the EMD performance and workings for all realized so far experiments) is determined by its built-in definitions and criteria and by the user supplied run-configuration vector Ψ as described in more details in Section 2.1

$$\Psi = (\Delta t, m, k, p \dots) \quad (1)$$

Vector Ψ is composed of empirical parameters supplied by a user when running HHT-DPS. Among these parameters are Δt – the sampling time interval in decimal fraction of seconds introduced by user with the HHT-DPS' Data Editor Option, m - the maximum number of allowable IMFs to strive for, and which is also selected by user for a run. Another parameter is k - the maximum allowable number of EMD sifts for one IMF. Parameter p allows user to select the "beyond-the-envelope-end-points" prediction algorithm option, for example the "pattern prediction" option. The following procedural formulation of the Empirical Mode Decomposition algorithm describes the EMD implementation in the latest version of HHT-DPS Release 1.4, the benchmark implementation of the HHT algorithms.

2.1 HHT-DPS EMD Algorithm

The EMD algorithm as implemented in the HHT-DPS, is based on a few distinct procedural steps (a) - (h):

a) EMD Algorithm Entry Point

Specify Input Signal Name and Sampling Interval

User specifies input signal $s(t)$ magnitudes $s(t_i)$ for equally spaced sequence of time t arguments t_i , $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$. User must enter the sampling time increment parameter Δt , using the EMD Data Editor Option. This parameter is required for a correct Hilbert spectrum derivation. In the first iteration of this algorithm the data parent signal $p(t_i)$ is the original input signal obtained by assigning the original signal $s(t_i)$ to the residue $R(t_i)$, which becomes $p(t_i)$ after Exit Criteria check branch "NO".

a1) Specify Run Configuration Vector

The user specifies the EMD run-configuration vector Ψ parameters as defined in (1).

a2) Initialize Arrays and Loop Counters

$j:=0$, where j is the number of IMFs found
 $R(t_i) := s(t_i)$, $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$
 $IMF_j(t_i)=0$, $j \in \{1 \dots m\}$, $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$

a3) EMD IMF Registry Entry Point

$R(t_i) := R(t_i) - IMF_j(t_i)$, $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$

(b) EMD Sifting Process Iterative Loop Entry Point

Find in the parent vector $p(t_i)$, $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$ two characteristic subsets which are obviously essential to any type of signal variation - the imbedded in the data itself subset of the local maxima extrema points p^{\max} and the subset of the local minima extrema points p^{\min} . The way these two subsets are further used by the EMD algorithm, as described next in (b), makes all the difference and dictates the results of the EMD sifting process. The computational complexity of the EMD algorithm actually depends on the sizes of p^{\max} and p^{\min} , rather than on the signal data vector's size N .

(c) **Extend** the sets p^{\max} and p^{\min} a bit beyond the data original argument interval $[t_1, t_N]$ with a few predicted maxima and minima extrema points on both ends of the original argument interval $[t_1, t_N]$. There are many prediction algorithms, meaning there is no accepted one. We provide a few predicting options in HHT-DPS. The extended extrema sets are then splined beyond original argument interval $[t_1, t_N]$ using predicted extrema points and then re-sampled on $[t_1, t_N]$. This original argument interval is always maintained throughout the HHT-DPS.

(d) **Spline** the two subsets for both extrema point types p^{\max} and p^{\min} extended sets using piecewise cubic splines [10]. The two resulting splines comprise the upper and lower (downward) boundary of the extrema subsets' envelope boundaries $u(t)$ and $d(t)$. The use of cubic spline provides a relatively slow changing background median $M(t)$ cubic spline (See (d) below) against which local fast variations of the signal become prominent and which, in turn, forms the basis for the most variant signal being sifted out first by the EMD sifting process.

(e) Form the Median

$u(t)$, $d(t)$ are re-sampled for sampling time arguments t_i , where $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$, and the discrete median vector $M(t_i)$ is computed as

$$M(t_i) = (u(t_i) + d(t_i)) / 2 \quad (2)$$

This definition of median is essential, because it assures the sifting process convergence. When the median computation is iterated k -times in the sifting process, the divisor becomes 2^k , which rapidly becomes a large number. The convergence theoretics are based on this number and are described in details in Sections 3-6.

(f) Form the Running Residue $r(t_i)$

The difference $r(t_i) = p(t_i) - M(t_i)$ is formed and the sifting residue $r(t_i)$ is checked against the IMF criteria, as follows

(g) The IMF Criteria Check

The number $E(r(t_i))$ of extrema points in $r(t_i)$, as well as the number $Z(r(t_i))$ of its zero-crossings (change in two adjacent extrema points' magnitude sign) in the following logical expression must hold the expression true. Namely, the IMF has more than 3 extrema points, and the difference of the number of extrema and zero-crossings is not more than 1

$$(E(r(t_i)) > 3) \ \&\& \ (|E(r(t_i)) - Z(r(t_i))| \leq 1), \ i \in \{1 \dots N\} \quad (3)$$

An $r(t_i)$, which satisfies the IMF Criteria, is called an IMF. It is stored during the EMD algorithm verification of the IMF Criteria and it is then subtracted from the signal residue $R(t)$ to obtain the EMD next sifting parent signal $p(t)$. This signal residue becomes the new input parent to the EMD sifting process iteration step.

Note, that at no time does a median $M(t)$ become an input to the EMD sifting process. The set of IMFs, which is derived from the data, comprises the signal $s(t)$ near-orthogonal adaptive basis and is used for the signal time-spectrum analysis.

If the sifting residue $r(t_i)$ satisfies the IMF Criteria the IMF is registered (stored in the IMF 2-D array) and control is passed to the Entry Point (*).

(h) Process Completion Criteria Check

If $r(t_i)$ is not an IMF it is checked here against the Exit Criteria

$$((E(r(t_i)) \leq 3) \text{ OR } (\#IMFs = m))$$

and when the criteria is satisfied the EMD sifting process completes with the last signal residue $R(t_m)$ becoming the process residue from which an IMF couldn't be made.

The EMD process completes and Exits at Point (*)**

Else (when $r(t_i)$ does not satisfy the above Exit Criteria) the control is passed to the **Entry Point (**)**

EMD Algorithm End.

2.1.1 EMD Algorithm Specific Requirements Definition of Extremas

For handling man-made pulse signals, which may have substantially large plateaus of sampled data points of equal magnitude, and to ensure the desired behavior of cubic splining for such signals, the definition of maxima and minima extrema points has been specifically modified in HHT-DPS implementation of the HHT as opposed to the standard mathematical definition. These are as follows:

s_i is a candidate extrema point if it satisfies the following general condition

$$((s_{i-1} < s_i) \text{ or } (s_{i-1} > s_i)) \quad (4)$$

A candidate extrema point s_i is a minima if it satisfies the following specific minima condition (it is an extrema candidate and there is a change of plateau end slope direction compared to the plateau input slope)

$$(s_{i-1} > s_i) \ \&\& \ (s_i = s_{i+1} = \dots = s_j < s_{j+1}) \quad (5)$$

A candidate extrema point s_i is a maxima if it satisfies the following specific maxima condition (it is an extrema candidate and there is a change of plateau end slope direction compared to the plateau input slope)

$$(s_{i-1} < s_i) \ \&\& \ (s_i = s_{i+1} = \dots = s_j > s_{j+1}) \quad (6)$$

2.1.2 EMD Algorithm Output

Naturally, because of the EMD algorithm construct, the sum of all IMF_j and the last signal residue $R(t_m)$ synthesize the

original input signal $s(t)$

$$s(t) = \sum IMF_j + R_m, \text{ where } 1 \leq j \leq m-1 \quad (7)$$

2.2 Problem Statement

With the EMD algorithm described above, the problem is to understand why the EMD works this way and try to develop the theoretical fundamentals of this algorithm.

3. HYPOTHESIS 1 AND THEORY OF THE EMD SIFTING PROCESS SEQUENCE OF SCALES

The fastest changing component of a composite signal is invariably being sifted out first in the Empirical Mode Decomposition algorithm and the first hypothesis in the development of the EMD algorithm' theory is related to the question "why?" This empirical fact is significant in that respect that it provides the first insight into how the EMD - algorithm works. Also the EMD algorithm's computational performance depends on the number of extrema in the input data set and taking out first all the extrema for the fastest varying component greatly contributes to the EMD algorithm's next IMF sifting steps' computational performance. Without the EMD algorithm being computationally effective it would be of little use to investigate it further.

3.1 Hypothesis 1, Sequence of Scales Example

Following is an example that depicts EMD process for a signal comprising different scales:

$$b1 = 1.0 \text{ (signal } s1 \text{ bias)}$$

$$s1 = b1 + 1.0 * \cos(2 * \pi * 1 * t)$$

$$s2 = 2.0 * \cos(2 * \pi * 2 * t)$$

$$s3 = 2.0 * \cos(2 * \pi * 50 * t)$$

$$s = s1 + s2 + s3$$

Figure 1. Signal $s = s1 + s2 + s3$

Figure 2. EMD Results for $s = s_1 + s_2 + s_3$

Hypothesis 1: Assuming theoretical convergence of the EMD sifting process, the fastest scale is being sifted out first, because the composite signal $s(t)$ extremas' envelope median is iteratively approximating the slower variance signal in presence of a fast varying component. When there is no such naturally slower varying component present, the EMD sifting process bravely makes one.

In order to prove this hypothesis we are now considering two analogies to the EMD sifting process - one from optical physics and the other from electrical and electronics engineering disciplines. The Figure 2 example and these analogies provide initial insight into why the signal fastest changing component (fastest scale) is being sifted out first by the EMD sifting process. In [14] we considered three examples of the EMD sifting for a few artificially created signals comprised of a fast and slow varying components. These analogies and intuitive examples allow to gain an initial insight into the mechanism of why the fastest scale gets sifted out first. We then examine the EMD sifting of an arbitrary signal and prove the hypothesis for a general case.

3.1 Analogy 1, Light Spectrum

The first analogy to EMD sifting has to do with light. Light spectral analysis, which has played such an important part in astronomical work, is essentially a method of ascertaining the nature of a remote celestial body by a process of sifting or analyzing into different components the light received from them [9]. A prism sifts out different colors. This known empirical phenomenon has a well-established theoretical basis in that the prism bends light of different wavelength by a different degree ρ , resulting in a distinctive order of output light spectrum (colors), with higher frequency components appearing "first" in the prism spectrum. It results in a definitive sequence of colors at the output of a prism.

3.2 Analogy 2, RC-Chain Filter

The second analogy to EMD sifting process has to do with an electrical RC-chain (circuitry). This circuitry is comprised of a resistor R and capacitor C with the RC-chain characteristic constant $\tau = RC$ as depicted in Figure 3. This circuitry is often used to smooth (filter out) fast variable fluctuations of a constant input voltage V_{in} [7]. The functioning of the RC-chain as a filter depends on its user selected hardware parameter, the characteristic constant τ .

Figure 3. RC-chain

The RC-chain's transfer function $K(\omega)$ for the corresponding amplitudes U_{in} and U_{out} of the signals V_{in} and V_{out} can be described as the ratio of the output voltage to input voltage amplitudes, with both voltages considered as a function of frequency ω :

$$K(\omega) = U_{out}(\omega) / U_{in}(\omega) = 1 / (\sqrt{1 + \omega^2 C^2 R^2})$$

or

$$K(\omega) = 1 / (\sqrt{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2}) \quad (8)$$

For a near-constant input voltage ($\omega=0$, absence of fluctuations) the capacitor impedance $X_C = 1/(\omega C) \rightarrow \infty$ and $K(0) = 1$. As $\omega \rightarrow \infty$, the capacitor impedance decreases, $X_C \rightarrow 0$, and $K(\omega)$ decreases, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. RC-chain Transfer Function for Amplitudes

The transfer function $K(\omega)$ was plotted for argument values $\omega = [0:1:2000]$ in Hz and $\tau = 0.01$ seconds. If we select the output voltage amplitude as a particular fraction of the input voltage, for example, as $K(\omega) = 0.707 = 1/\sqrt{2}$ (this threshold value is selected to get the following convenient computations and it is the rms of a sin function over one period), then the corresponding frequency band ω_B or filter boundary can be evaluated from the transfer function $K(\omega)$ as follows:

$$1 / \sqrt{2} = 1 / \sqrt{(1 + \omega_B^2 \tau^2)}$$

or

$$(1 + \omega_B^2 \tau^2) = 2 \rightarrow \omega_B^2 \tau^2 = 1 \rightarrow \omega_B \tau = 1$$

or

$$\omega_B = 1 / \tau$$

Frequencies higher than ω_B are filtered out (sifted out) by this RC-chain filter and the stability of the output increases as the RC-chain's constant τ increases. The above example and analogies provide a framework for the proof of Hypothesis 1.

3.3 Proof of Hypothesis 1

The Hypothesis 1 is proved by considering two instances of the general case of an arbitrary signal $s(t)$ viewed as being comprised of two components – a relatively fast or high time-varying component $s_h(t)$ and a slower or low time-varying component $s_l(t)$, similar to signals in analogies and intuitive examples

$$s(t) = s_h(t) + s_l(t)$$

3.3.1 Two Instances of a General Case Signal

3.3.1.1 A signal with fast varying component extrema symmetry

The first instance is of a signal with symmetry defined as

$$|(\max)s_h(t)| - |(\min)s_h(t)| \approx 0$$

In such an instance of local symmetry we can approximate the signal maxima and minima envelope spline values $s^{\max}(t)$ and $s^{\min}(t)$ as

$$s^{\max}(t) \approx s_l(t) + |(\max)s_h(t)|$$

$$s^{\min}(t) \approx s_l(t) - |(\min)s_h(t)|$$

for any t on small interval $[t_1, t_1 + \delta t]$. The signal envelope's median $M(t)$ on interval $[t_1, t_1 + \delta t]$ is weaving along the signal slow varying component because by definition

$$M(t) = (s^{\max}(t) + s^{\min}(t)) / 2 \approx s_l(t)$$

and

$$s(t) - M(t) = s(t) - s_l(t) = s_h(t) \rightarrow \text{IMF.}$$

3.3.1.2 A signal with slow varying component allowing linear approximation

The slow varying component allows linear approximation. Whilst, another, more formal than in the first instance, approach in explaining why the fastest scale is being sifted our first is to consider the approximation of the slow varying signal component $s_l(t)$ on a small interval $t \in [t_1, t_1 + \delta t]$ by a straight line passing through the interval two end points (linear approximation is here actually the definition of a slow varying component)

$$\{ (t_1, s_l(t_1)), (t_1 + \delta t, s_l(t_1 + \delta t)) \}$$

or

$$(s_l(t) - s_l(t_1)) / (t - t_1) = (s_l(t_1 + \delta t) - s_l(t_1)) / \delta t = k$$

or

$$s_l(t) \approx (s_l(t_1 + \delta t) - s_l(t_1)) / \delta t = s_l(t_1) + k*(t - t_1)$$

or

$$s_l(t) \approx s_l(t_1) + k*(t - t_1)$$

Slope k is negligible small because of the selection of $s_l(t)$ as the slow varying component and thus the straight line is being almost parallel to the time axis for small time argument intervals. A fast time-varying oscillation component, combined with a line segment, must satisfy the above approximate equality.

This leads to a median point $M(t)$ for any $t \in [t_1, t_1 + \delta t]$

$$M(t) = ((s_l(t_1) + k*(t - t_1)) + (\max)s_h(t)) + ((s_l(t_1) + k*(t - t_1)) + (\min)s_h(t))) / 2 =$$

$$s_l(t_1) + k*(t - t_1) \approx s_l(t_1) \approx s_l(t)$$

The resulting median point is being situated approximately on the slower varying component $s_l(t)$. When the median, approximated by $s_l(t)$, is subtracted from the signal we get the fastest varying component of the signal $s_h(t) \rightarrow \text{IMF}$.

3.3.2 General Case Signal

We now consider an arbitrary signal, as well as the use of piecewise cubic splines for signal envelope construction and spline role in the EMD sifting scale sequence generation. The above two signal instances were studied for very small intervals δt . However, the selection of a piecewise straight line approximation for the signal envelope boundaries $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ on large intervals between two adjacent extrema points of the same type, appeared to be unproductive for EMD implementation during the development of the HHT-DPS engineering tool. Instead EMD and HHT-DPS use a widely researched in digital signal processing alternative, the piecewise cubic spline interpolation. The complete proof for the general case signal was presented in [14].

4. HYPOTHESIS 2 AND THEORY OF LOCAL SYMMETRY INVARIANCE AND IMF STRUCTURE

The EMD algorithm is using the extrema envelope’s median definition (2). This allows the following hypothesis that is significant in the understanding of why the EMD sifting process works the way it does.

Hypothesis 2: The EMD sifting process preserves an intermediate locally symmetric zero-crossing pair of extrema points with interleaved regions of diminishing amplitudes yielding an IMF with a definitive structure.

4.1 The Median and Hypothesis 2 Relation

The EMD Median Construction and the Hypothesis 2 of Symmetric Zero-Crossing Pairs’ Invariance and Interleaving Regions of Diminishing Amplitudes are closely related.

To prove this hypothesis we observe how the EMD constructs the envelop functions $u(t)$, $d(t)$ using piecewise cubic splines and then re-samples them at original time sampling points t_i which it needs to compute the median point $(u(t_i) + d(t_i))/2$. Only if a point does not already exist on $u(t)$ or $d(t)$, it is re-sampled and produced (at t_i which is not an extrema argument two re-sampled points are produced and for extrema time arguments t_j a single re-sample point is produced). In general, consider a resulting pair of sampled signal envelope splines’ values at extrema time argument t_i

$$\{u(t_i) \equiv 10.0, d(t_i) \equiv 5.0\}$$

The median of these two points is $M(t_i) \equiv (10.0 + 5.0)/2 = 7.5$. One, and only one of these two $u(t_i)$ or $d(t_i)$ points at t_i , is always a new (re-sampled) point. This is because of the definition of an extrema point – it can only be a maxima or it can only be a minima at an extrema time argument t_i , and it can’t be both. Lets say that the maxima point at t_i , $u(t_i)=10.0$ is the actual data maxima point and that the other point (5.0) is being the new data point obtained by re-sampling the lower envelope cubic spline. We observe that when $M(t)$ is subtracted from the parent signal the nearest maxima and minima to t_i become +2.5 and approximately – 2.5 correspondently. The next median for this pair of adjusted extremas becomes 0.0. Whilst, this pair of $\{+2.5, -2.5\}$ satisfies the condition of a zero-crossing (two adjacent extrema magnitudes have opposite signs) and since it is a symmetric zero-crossing (the two extrema absolute amplitudes are approximately equal), it is not affected anymore by the rest of the sifting process. The EMD sifting now continues until the next pair of symmetric zero-crossing is achieved or the parent signal amplitude envelope band approaches 0. This assures the emergence of an IMF, if it was present in the signal, or if it is not in the signal it is being “cut out as an IMF” from the signal. This process is represented pictorially in the following Figure 5.

The first cardinal point in Hypothesis 2 proof is depicted in Figure 5. The EMD sifting process results in a combination of local feature representing an Invariant extrema pair capture and global feature represented by continuous diminishing amplitudes non-invariant areas of convergence for more invariant pairs, if any, when cubic splines are used. The sifting process results in a “chain-like” structure shown in Figure 6. The EMD sifting process preserves a symmetric zero-crossing pair of points, once such a pair has been found or made, and the sifting process continues on the remainder of the parent signal.

Figure 5. EMD Sifting Process Generation of Invariant Symmetric Extrema Pairs

The difference between piecewise line (segment) approximation for the signal envelopes and the piecewise cubic spline curves now becomes more clear, namely:

The line segment envelopes $u(t)$, $d(t)$ provide a near convex-concave envelope which results in a fast direct conversion. However, the line segments interpolation does not select or make pairs of symmetric extrema, even when they exist or when they are possible to visualize and being generated by the sifting process. The cubic spline also allows preserving enough information in the non-invariant convergence region by specifying the configuration vector parameter k .

On the other hand, the central property (and this makes the difference) of a piecewise cubic spline is that it is the lowest degree polynomial that has a closed form solution for its coefficients and that has enough flexibility to facilitate selection, and then retaining as an invariant, a symmetric pair of adjacent extrema for the remainder of the sifting process convergence (a second degree polynomial choice for convex envelopes is, for example, to use convex semicircles built on each maxima extrema pair line segment as diameter, and concave semicircles for minima points. Although computationally simple this choice quickly leads to more difficult problems). As a consequence the EMD sifting process leads to such possible results when using cubic splines:

- The residue happens to be obviously asymmetric but satisfies the IMF Criteria and is immediately selected as an IMF
- There exist a symmetric signal and EMD just sifts out the fastest symmetric signal
- When there is none of the above two cases the EMD will bravely make a structured IMF.

4.2 IMF structure

The EMD sifting process, using cubic spline interpolation for the envelopes $u(t)$, $d(t)$, encounters (or makes) a pair of symmetric extrema points that become an invariant in the remainder of the sifting process. The continuation of sifting after that may find (or make) the next symmetric pair of extremas or converge in between these invariant pairs of selected extremas to near-zero amplitudes which results in an IMF component $S(t)$ of a definitive structure, as shown in the following Figure 6.

Figure 6. EMD Sifting Process General Result: IMF of a Definitive Structure

The first cardinal point in Hypothesis 2 was made in Section 4.1 and Figure 5. The second cardinal point in Hypothesis 2 is that the general result of the EMD sifting process is an IMF of a definitive structure. An IMF is a near-zero-offset curve, which is connecting sparse clusters of near-symmetric extrema pairs. This point is demonstrated in Figure 6.

4.3 On the Construction of the Signal Extrema Envelope Boundaries

Independent of the choice of method used to construct $u(t)$ and $d(t)$, such as line segments or piecewise cubic spline, the two functions $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ are used to represent the signal $s(t)$ envelope for the purpose of finding the envelope's median $M(t) = (u(t) + d(t)) / 2$. $M(t)$ is an interpolation function, as are $u(t)$ and $d(t)$, that is constructed on the set of maxima extrema points and correspondently minima extrema points $p^{\max}(t)$, $p^{\min}(t)$.

The polynomials $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ are re-sampled over all data sampling times t_i , $i \in \{1 \dots N\}$ and $M(t)$ is computed for all points. Say, if we are re-sampling at t_k , there are always two piecewise segments of $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ such that argument t_k belongs to these two polynomials' domain intersection and can also be expressed as the sum of the $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ intersection pieces

$$u(t) = a_1 + b_1 * t + c_1 * t^2 + d_1 * t^3 \quad i_1 \leq t_k \leq j_1$$

$$d(t) = a_2 + b_2 * t + c_2 * t^2 + d_2 * t^3 \quad i_2 \leq t_k \leq j_2$$

$$M(t) = (a_1 + a_2)/2 + ((b_1 + b_2)/2)t + ((c_1 + c_2)/2)t^2 + ((d_1 + d_2)/2)t^3$$

For maxima extrema times t_i^{ext} we have that $p(t_i^{\max})$ are the maxima extrema and $p(t_i^{\min})$ are the minima extrema. The value $p(t_i^{\text{ext}}) - M(t_i^{\text{ext}})$ would change the extremas at re-sampling time unless $M(t_i^{\text{ext}}) = 0.0$ (symmetric case). In this case the symmetric extrema point pairs remain invariant. More details on the symmetry arising from the sifting process are given below in Section 4.4. The other cardinal point is to observe that $M(t)$, because of its definition as a linear combination of two splines $u(t)$ and $d(t)$, is also a piecewise cubic spline.

When $M(t)$ is re-sampled at all sampling times, the re-sampled $M(t)$ points are all situated on corresponding $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ piecewise splines comprising $M(t)$. For invariant pairs the maxima pair and minima pair interval re-sampling points remain on the pair splines and when re-splining is done it results in approximately the same splines in such pair's regions as a step before and this contributes to EMD algorithm convergence. Lets now consider the origin of invariant pairs in the EMD sifting process.

4.4 On the EMD Sifting Process' Origin of Adjacent Extrema Maxima and Minima Point Symmetry

Given signal $r(t)$ as input to the EMD sifting process, consider the signal's envelope upper and lower boundary functions (piecewise cubic splines) $u(t)$, $d(t)$. Let us take a look at the behavior of this envelope' median as defined by

$$M(t) = (u(t) + d(t)) / 2$$

$M(t)$ is obtained by re-sampling $u(t)$, $d(t)$ when they do not have original data points from $r(t)$ belonging to these two curves. This is obvious for all time arguments that were not extrema points in $r(t)$ and when both $u(t)$ and $d(t)$ must be re-sampled. At time arguments were $r(t)$ had extremas one of the two following cases takes place – there is a maxima extrema only or exclusively there is a minima extrema only at t_i , namely $a = u(t_i)$ or $b = d(t_i)$

4.4.1 Case of maxima extrema point at t_i

Consider that at re-sampling time argument t_i we have $u(t_i) = \mathbf{a}$ and $d(t_{i+1}) = \mathbf{b}$, where \mathbf{a} is a maximum. Then

$$M(t_i) \approx (a + b)/2$$

Let us now examine the new signal $r(t)$ evaluated as

$$r(t) = r(t) - M(t)$$

Because in this case there is a maxima extrema at t_i , we have

$$r(t_i) = u(t_i) = a$$

Lets make a strong assumption (which we already made evaluating $M(t_i)$) that $b \approx d(t_{i+1})$.

The weaker assumption is also sufficient for these

considerations and this assumption makes sense for cubic splines $u(t)$, $d(t)$ and $M(t)$ $d(t_j) = b \leq a$.

Then at this extrema time argument the new signal point that is going into the next sifting pass is

$$r(t_j) = r(t_j) - M(t_j) \approx a - (a + b)/2 = (a - b)/2 \geq 0$$

Expression $(a-b)$ is positive when re-sampling time point has a maximum extrema, as in this case, and thus represents the width of the envelope at time argument t_j . It is then obvious that the new signal point at extrema time argument of in this case is located inside the previous signal envelope and is approximately at the mid-point of the envelope cut at t_j , as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Re-Sampling Argument Maxima

4.4.2 Case of minima extrema point at t_j

When at a re-sampling time argument there is a minima, as shown in Figure 8, the new signal point (function of parent signal and median arguments) appears on the negative (on the other side) of the time axis at ordinate value

$$r(t_j) = r(t_j) - M(t_j) \approx a - (a + b)/2 = (a - b)/2 \leq 0$$

Figure 8. Re-Sampling Argument Minima

The EMD sifting process will rapidly balance the position of the $r(t_j)$ point around the abscissa region of small magnitudes or quickly induce symmetry of adjacent extremas of different types when symmetry is not prominent in the input signal.

We have demonstrated the origin of symmetric pairs generation during the EMD sifting process and that an IMF has a distinctive structure. This completes the proof the EMD sifting process Hypothesis 2 of preserving (invariant) symmetric extrema pairs generated by the EMD sifting process. This, in turn, completes the proof of Hypothesis 1 formulated in Section 2 and in [14] and lays the foundation for the proof of the EMD sifting process rapid convergence in diminishing amplitude areas in the following Section 5.

5. HYPOTHESIS 3 AND THEORY OF THE EMD ALGORITHM RAPID CONVERGENCE ORDER

The empirical experience provided by the above example and reported in [14] demonstrates that the EMD sifting process, as implemented in HHT-DPS, apparently converges and that the convergence is also fast. However, it is not obvious why? We are now formulating a hypothesis of why it works this way and derive the order of convergence.

Hypothesis 3: The convergence of the EMD sifting process is of order $O(1/2^{k-1})$. This is a consequence of the EMD envelope control points definition as sets of extremas of the same type, its interpolation by piecewise cubic spline whose control points are the data extremas, and envelope's median construction as an arithmetic median - the envelopes' sum divided by 2.

A different EMD implementation case of extrema envelope construction, as described below, could make this convergence obvious. Although it would not yield any additional information about the signal spectrum, it does illuminate some important points about the EMD workings.

To revisit, the EMD deals with signal $s(t_j)$, a digital (discrete) signal obtained from measurements at even sampling time intervals $t = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N\}$. Here interpolation of some kind becomes necessary for the signal data processing. However, if we still to consider the contiguous composite signal $s(t)$, then the signal itself connects its maxima points and becomes its envelope's upper boundary $u(t)$. In the same way, the signal $s(t)$ may be considered its envelope's lower (down) boundary $d(t)$. As a consequence, the EMD median with this choice of envelope boundaries, would be

$$M(t) = (u(t) + d(t))/2 = 2s(t)/2 = s(t)$$

The EMD convergence process would be completed in one sifting step. But we did not gain anything by attempting this perfection in constructing the extremas' envelope and by using all the data points and achieving a one-step convergence. The entire $s(t)$ becomes the EMD invariant and the output equals to the input. This leads to fastest convergence of the EMD process without deriving any new

For the EMD sifting process parent signal extrema envelope using piecewise cubic polynomials p_i , $0 < i < N-1$

$$p_i(t) = a_i + b_i * t + c_i * t^2 + d_i * t^3$$

The $R_{n,i}$ remainder term's index is $n=4$ and

$$s^3(t) = 6d_i = \int s^4(t) dt \text{ on } [t_i, t_{i+1}]$$

We can then estimate the remainder term as

$$R_{n,i} \leq s^4(t_j) * ((t_j - t_i)^n / 4!) < 6d_i * N^4 / 4! = O(h^4) = 6d_i * N^4 / 1 * 2 * 3 * 4 = d_i * N^4 / 4$$

For all practical purposes

$$G < \max(R_{n,i}) < O(h^4), \quad 0 \leq i \leq N-1$$

For example, in the expansion of a sinusoid $A * \cos(2 * \pi * f * t)$ into a Taylor series with $n-1$ terms, the remainder term upper bound can be estimated as follows

$$R_{n,i} \leq A(2 * \pi * f)^n * |\cos(2 * \pi * f * t)| * N^n \leq A(2 * \pi * f)^n * 1.0 * N^n = A * (2 * \pi * f * N)^n$$

or for a piecewise cubic spline expansion

$$G \leq A * (2 * \pi * f * N)^4$$

This number G quickly becomes smaller than 2^k , namely for

$$k > \log(A * (2 * \pi * f * N)^4 / 2) \quad (10)$$

The EMD sifting process running signal envelope is depicted above in Figure 6. Here the symmetric pair's median is already an invariant and close to zero inside the bulges. It keeps converging to near-zero amplitudes within the narrow channels between the invariant bulges.

This completes the proof of the EMD sifting process rapid convergence Hypothesis 3 and explains the convergence order $O(1/2^{k-1})$, as well as adds more insight into the significance of the piecewise cubic spline interpolation of the signal envelope boundaries - that it preserves as invariant the symmetric pairs of adjacent extremas as stipulated in Hypothesis 2.

6. ON SIGNAL SYNTHESIS APPLICATIONS AND LEVELS

In any of the known spectral analysis and synthesis techniques the idea is to map the signal functionally described in continuous time domain into a more compact domain (for example, the frequency domain) that is more susceptible for considerations. The time domain is usually comprised of an infinite set of arguments, say rational numbers, whose power is larger than that of a countable

infinite set of natural numbers. Mapping the problem into a countable set (like Fourier Transform coefficients) may simplify the problem and yet lead to closed form solutions. For example, for certain real time functions that satisfy the Dirichlet conditions, the problem of spectral analysis and synthesis can be mapped from continuous infinite domain of a real time interval into three countable sets by the Fourier Integral Transform – a set of frequencies $\{\omega_0, 2\omega_0 \dots n\omega_0 \dots\}$ which pre-describe the infinite but countable basis of spectral functions (sinusoids) and their corresponding amplitude coefficients $\{a_n\}$, $\{b_n\}$ (Fourier Transform coefficients). The Inverse Fourier Transform is used for signal synthesis and different subsets of the basis are used for different filter implementations of signal synthesis. The Fourier Transform has an Inverse. However, with other mapping functions, finding the Inverse is a very difficult problem. In most cases the Inverse does not exist. When it does exist, it is very computationally intensive to find it.

The Hilbert-Huang Transform is a Digital Signal Processing Transform. Its domain is a finite set of N sample points $\{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_i, \dots, t_N\}$. The HHT facilitates signal synthesis on two levels described below. The basis for this synthesis is the 1-to-1 mapping of each input pixel locality to each IMF point locality and determined by the same corresponding index $i=1, \dots, N$ in their stored arrays. This is obvious. What is not transparent is that the Hilbert Spectrum stored array has the same property of 1-to-1 mapping in relation to its source IMFs. This becomes apparent by direct examination of the discrete Hilbert Transform algorithm. It then allows a direct inverse from a Hilbert Spectrum array to its IMF and consequently to its origin locality in the $s(t)$ signal for selected index $i=1, \dots, N$, as well as for any subset of points in the Hilbert Spectrum 2-D array. The synthesis from the Hilbert Spectrum color display of the Hilbert Spectrum 2-D array and corresponding amplitudes becomes counter-intuitive. On the color Hilbert Spectrum picture some signal features may become obvious, but the feature inverse may seem difficult because it is not obvious in the Hilbert Spectrum 2-D array where the display color pixel originated. However, the graphical interface knows for sure where the source pixel is. For example, the Microsoft Paint Application (Trademark of Microsoft Corporation), allows a user to “paint” (mark, select) some areas on the screen, which results in automatic construction of a map between each pixel location on the screen and its corresponding pixel in the 2-D source data array. This, in turn, provides the theoretical foundation for the signal synthesis using the IMFs and the Hilbert Spectrum 2-D array or its display color picture as described below.

6.1 HHT Synthesis Levels

Synthesis in any spectrum determination theory involves construction of an inverse function and that invariably seems to be a difficult problem. We will investigate two levels of synthesis in the HHT-DPS using the signal Intrinsic Mode Functions and the Hilbert Spectrum.

6.1.1 Level 1 Synthesis Using IMFs

First, the HHT EMD delivers the time domain signal decomposition into a finite base of (m-1) near-orthogonal time domain IMFs and Residue function R, derived from the signal. Because of the IMFs' construction, they represent different time scales and these can be used for filtering out different time varying components, and synthesize the filtered signal by just summing up remaining IMFs and the Residue of interest with different weights w_j , for example using $w_j = 0, 1$ or

$$S(t) = \sum w_j * IMF_j + w_m * R_m, \quad 1 < j < m-1 \quad (11)$$

6.1.2 Level 2 Synthesis Using Hilbert Spectrum

The second level of synthesis in the HHT is based on its Hilbert Spectrum. Although the Hilbert Spectrum represents Instantaneous Frequencies, for which there is no known Inverse transformation, we can still construct a direct reverse mapping from the Hilbert Spectrum domain into the IMF time domain and further into the signal $s(t)$ time domain as described above in expression (11). Namely, an original signal pixel $s(t_j)$ can be filtered using weights w_j and then synthesized from IMFs and residue R as

$$s(t_j) = \sum IMF_j(t_j) + R_m(t_j)$$

Each IMF pixel at t_j directly corresponds to the signal single pixel at t_j . This facilitates the Level 1 signal synthesis because this is the Inverse mapping. The Hilbert Spectrum becomes more computationally complex. Namely, the Hilbert Spectrum $H_i = H(IMF_i)$ is computed for each IMF_i . The Hilbert Spectrum H_i^j is actually a function (mapping) of $IMF_j(t_i)$ into a pair of {Instantaneous Frequency, Amplitude} or

$$H_i^j = H_i^j(F_i^j, A_i^j) = C(i, j)$$

where both components – Instantaneous Frequency F_i^j and associated amplitude A_i^j have been derived from a signal component $IMF_j(t_i)$ and where $C(i, j)$ is color code value.

The 2-D color graph of the Hilbert Spectrum is actually constructed of all IMF_j ($1 \leq j \leq m$). Inasmuch, each geometrical point of the Hilbert Spectrum Graph originates in some IMF. There are up to m-points on each vertical cut of the Hilbert Spectrum Graph. In order to trace the origin of each of these m points to one of the m IMFs we must only carry with each color graph pixel, in addition to its obvious time reference t_i , its IMF origin index j. This is the concept of Inverse mapping. Computationally it can be done without any change to the EMD or the Hilbert Spectrum algorithm's implementation in HHT-DPS. Namely, for any of the possible pixels on graph's Windows Array painted (selected) subset $\{F, C, t\}$ it is sufficient to map pair (F, C) by direct comparison with any of the m-IMF derived $\{F, A\}$ arrays. A pair $\#j \{F_i^j, A_i^j\}$ in any IMF can be used for signal pixel synthesis at t_i . For example, we have used this synthesis technique for signal synthesis by "painting" a

recognizable 2-D pattern in Hilbert Spectrum image and then tracing back (Direct Inversion) the painted subset of pixels to their origins in the IMF pixels (whatever pixels were found first to match the Hilbert Spectrum pixel values), and then deleting them from the IMFs (zeroing out their amplitudes in the IMF). This then allows the synthesis of the portion of the input signal from the modified IMFs and which then depicts the extracted feature as being successfully removed from the signal.

CONCLUSIONS

We have reported the initial theoretical proof of why the fastest changing component of a composite signal is being sifted out first in the Empirical Mode Decomposition sifting process as implemented in the HHT-DPS. We have also provided the theoretical explanation of why the EMD algorithm converges and converges rapidly while using cubic splines for signal envelope interpolation. As part of this research we developed a few practical techniques for cutting a large input data set into smaller files, which facilitates faster HHT-DPS processing of large sound files. We have also developed in parallel with this investigation a few related applications. For example, we have developed one of the first techniques for signal synthesis using the Hilbert Spectrum, by "painting" a recognizable 2-D pattern in Hilbert Spectrum image and then tracing back (direct inversion) the painted subset pixels to their origin in the IMFs, and deleting them from the IMFs. This allows reconstruction of the portion of the input signal from the modified IMFs with the selected feature being successfully removed. Future work includes research on the IMFs basis orthogonality, the affects of normalization on the Hilbert Transform and resulting instantaneous frequency, as well as further research in the 2-D signal processing domain and handling of intermittency. The HHT is a relatively new method in signal processing and further development of the HHT is in progress [15], [16].

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